

**A HOME LIFE EXPERIENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF
ENGLISH AND URDU MEDIUM SCHOOLS****Dr. Ashwini Karwande,***Assistant Professor,**Department of Education,**University of Mumbai***Introduction**

The scientific developments and subsequent technological revolutions have influenced the family pattern to a great extent. Joint or extended families of the good old days are no longer as common as they once were. Breakdown of joint family system and huge migration of rural men- folk to urban and suburban clusters have resulted in the emergence of nuclear families and increase of women headed household. All these changes have played a transforming trick with both the social and physical environments enjoyed by the child (Youssef, N. & Hertler, C.B. 1984).

Due to rapid urbanization and increase in number of small families the children, nowadays are being deprived of their former human as well as infrahuman companions. Increasingly the socio- cultural complex of the modern children mostly in urban areas- has been confined to the dimension of a few rooms in an apartment.. These deprivations either negate or hinder the overall social, cultural and physical development of young children all over the world. Hence, it is argued by many experts that the provision of institutionalized care and education for younger children would minimize this deprivation and help the nation to build up a strong and efficient human capital.

The need of the new social setup is to accept the family as an educational force for all the members of the society, more particularly for the younger members. The need of today is to realize and accept the fact that.The song a father sings to his child in the morning, or a story that a mother reads to her child before bed help lay the foundations for a child's life and in turn for our nation's future (Clinton, H.R. 1997).

The home also acts as the pivotal center at which the interaction of the inner and cultural forces of young children is more significantly expressed. Moreover family is the first 'social environment' that a child encounters in this world. So the fact that children figuratively bring their families to school can neither be ignored nor undermined.

Need of the Study

From the review of the related literature, many studies have been conducted on home life experience of students. As far as researcher's knowledge a single study was not found to compare the home life experience of students studying in English and Urdu medium school. As such interest in this topic grew stronger. Since home environment, educational encouragements, family climate, peer group participation, and extracurricular activities all play an important role in the development of a child. Therefore it is very necessary to assess all these variables. It is necessary to assess the home environment of children to know the inconvenience that they find at home. Keeping this as the main objective, the present study is undertaken to assess the home life experience of the student.

Statement of the Problem

"A Comparative Study of Home Life Experience of Secondary School Students on the Basis of School Types"

Operational Definitions Of Variables:

Home Life Experience: For the purpose of the present study, 'Home Life Experience' has been defined as how a student experiences at home and related to perceived psychological environment of home. It also deals with the physical aspect of home environment and it consisted of the following four factors.

Each of the factors is defined as follows:

a) Educational Encouragement: It means all support provided by the parents to their children to develop their unique abilities, and satisfy their interest and curiosity to develop educational interest and better educational opportunities like private study room, learning materials and better schooling at home.

b) Family Climate: This includes the tendency of parent to take care of their child's physical, psychological and social requirements, so that the child grows happily. This involves all caring and supporting functions of the parents in the family.

c) Peer Group Participation: It indicates the democratic atmosphere of home in which children get opportunities to play with peers. Children learn many skills through play with other children. There is no substitute for the experience children gain from interacting with peers.

d) Extracurricular Activities: It means the encouragement given by the members of family to extracurricular activities such as participation and proficiency in easy competition, oratorical contest and games, involvement in group work such as taking part in dramas, ability in histrionic talent and the liking for excursion etc. The essential aspect of activities includes under it is the recognition of their active interest and deep involvement in school activities other than academic ones and ability to associate with other pupils. It also reveals their multifaceted interests and well developed personality.

Aim of the Study

To study and compare the home life experience of secondary school students of English and Urdu medium.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To compare the home life experience of secondary school students with respect to the following factors.
 - (a) Educational Encouragement
 - (b) Family Climate
 - (c) Peer Group Participation
 - (d) Extra Curricular Activities
- 2) To compare the home life experience of
 - i. English medium and
 - ii. Urdu medium
 School students on the basis of gender with respect to the following factors.
 - (a) Educational Encouragement

- (b) Family Climate
- (c) Peer Group Participation
- (d) Extra Curricular Activities

3) To compare the home life experience of secondary school students on the basis of gender.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The present study investigates into the home life experience of secondary school students. For this purpose a comparative approach was adopted. The study is restricted to Secondary schools situated in Greater Mumbai only and not to the other parts of Maharashtra. The study is quantitative in nature. The study is restricted to the students from secondary schools only. The study is restricted only to the English and Urdu medium schools and does not include Marathi, Gujarati or any other medium schools.

Methodology of the Study

The present study is of quantitative descriptive type and adopted casual comparative method as it is aimed to compare students 'home life experience' on the basis of their school types and gender.

Sample of the Study

The sample selected for the present study consisted of students, both boys and girls from secondary schools situated in Greater Mumbai and affiliated to Maharashtra State Board. Data are collected from 12 schools situated in greater Mumbai out of which 6 schools from English medium and 6 schools from Urdu medium. The size of the final sample is 595 of which students of English medium are 284, which included 150 girls and 134 boys and Urdu medium are 311, which included 143 girls and 168 boys.

Tools Used For the Study

The researcher used Personal data sheet and Home life experience scale for data collection. The home life experience scale was a readily available tool prepared by D. Hemalata Kalimathi and D. Kumaran (2008). The researcher has translated this tool in Urdu language for Urdu medium students with the help of Ms. Rukhsana Kamil, M.Ed. student, Department of Education and validated with the experts in Urdu language.

Major Findings of the Study:

1. There is a significant difference in the scores of home life experience of English and Urdu medium school students.

TABLE 1

Difference in Student's Home Life Experience Scores of English and Urdu Medium School Students

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	't' ratio
Home Life Experience	English medium	284	31.38	4.62	8.54**
	Urdu medium	311	27.62	6.14	

The mean scores of English medium students are higher than the Urdu medium students. The English medium students have been perceived good home environment and experiences as compared to Urdu medium students.

2. There is a significant difference in the scores of educational encouragement, family climate, peer group participation and extracurricular activities of English and Urdu medium students. The English medium students have been perceived better educational encouragement, family climate, peer group participation and extracurricular activities as compared to Urdu medium students. (Table 2)

TABLE 2

Difference in Student's Home Life Experience In Terms Of Factors for English and Urdu Medium School Students

Students	N	Educational Encouragement		t-ratio	Family Climate		t-ratio	Peer Group Participation		t-ratio	Extra Curricular Activities		t-ratio
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD		Mean	SD		Mean	SD	

				n		n		n					
English medium	284	7.09	1.39	2.29*	8.96	1.7	10.18**	8.31	1.66	4.35**	7	1.58	10.9**
Urdu medium	311	6.77	1.61		7.23	2.24		7.7	2.02		5.91	2.11	

Figure 1 gives bar graph showing the mean scores of home life experience in terms of 'Educational Encouragement (EE)' 'Family Climate (FC)' 'Peer Group Participation (PGP)' 'Extra Curricular Activities (ECA)' of English and Urdu medium school students

Figure 1

Bar graph showing the mean scores of home life experience in terms of 'Educational Encouragement (EE)' 'Family Climate (FC)' 'Peer Group Participation (PGP)' 'Extra Curricular Activities (ECA)' Of English And Urdu Medium School Students

3. There is a significant difference in the home life experience score of English medium girls and boys. The mean scores of English medium girls is higher than the boys. The English medium girls have been perceived good home environment and experiences as compared to English medium boys. But there is no significant difference in the home life experience score of Urdu medium girls and boys. The Urdu medium girls and boys have been perceived same home environment and experiences. (Table 3)

TABLE 3
Difference In Student's Home Life Experience Scores Of English
And Urdu Medium School Students On The Basis Of Gender

Groups	N	Mean	SD	't' ratio
English Medium Girls	150	32.53	4.33	4.60**
English Medium Boys	134	30.09	4.61	
Urdu Medium Girls	143	28.10	6.77	1.25
Urdu Medium Boys	168	27.22	5.33	

4. There is a significant difference in the home life experience factors English and Urdu medium students on the basis of gender. In all the factors mean score of English medium girls is higher than Urdu medium girls. This shows that the home life experience for English medium girls is better than Urdu medium girls.

For boys no significant difference was found in the factors Educational Encouragement and Peer Group Participation. The mean score for Educational Encouragement and Peer Group Participation is more or less same. But a significant difference was found for Family Climate and Extra Curricular Activities factors. The mean score are higher for English medium boys than Urdu medium boys.

TABLE 4

Difference In Student's Home Life Experience Factors English Medium Students On The Basis Of Gender

	N	Educational Encouragement		t-ratio	Family Climate		t-ratio	Peer Group Participation		t-ratio	Extra Curricular Activities		t-ratio				
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD		Mean	SD		Mean	SD					
English medium girls	150	7.26	1.4	2.19*	9.35	1.48	8.78**	8.63	1.47	4.35**	7.28	1.41	4.37**				
Urdu medium girls	143	6.87	1.63		7.23	2.5		7.65	2.28		6.34	2.17					
English medium Boys	134	6.91	1.36		1.35	8.33		1.82	4.99**		7.95	1.78		1.12	6.68	1.7	5.36**
Urdu medium Boys	168	6.68	1.59			7.23		2			7.75	1.17			5.54	1.99	

Discussions:

From the data it has been found that the Urdu medium school students belong to middle class and lower middle class families. The parents of Urdu medium school students are unable to fulfill students' needs. Parents are unable to provide the proper knowledge to their children because mostly parents are illiterate. Hence probably due to their illiteracy students of Urdu medium don't pay the attention on study. They are unable to concentrate. As compared to Urdu medium students, English medium students' home background is better. In some cases, children have separate room for study and conducive and supporting modes of education. But Urdu medium students do not have any facilities at home. English medium students' parents are serious regarding education of their children but the Urdu medium parents are not very keen regarding it.

The mean scores of English medium students in educational encouragement, one of the factors of home life experience, are higher than the Urdu medium students. This could be due to the fact that Urdu medium parents' socio-economic status is not good. They try to provide good education to their children but they do not have enough money to spend on them. But English medium students parents have better socio-economic status. They are more educated and highly conscious regarding their children. This could be the main reason for high mean score of English medium students.

Also it has been found that the mean scores of secondary girls in educational encouragement are higher than the boys. This could be due to the reason that now days' girls are getting equal opportunities from their parents and they are utilizing these opportunities in a proper manner. They are also very serious regarding their studies. The boys also getting the opportunities from their parents but they are not taking advantage of these opportunities very well. This could be the reason of low mean score of boys.

For the factor family climate mean scores of English medium students are higher than the Urdu medium students. This could be due to the fact that family climate is one of the most important thing for improvement of home life experience at home. If the parents take all care and provide good things such as food, clothes money, educational things and life style things to their children it affects on children psychology and develop their social relationship and improve

students life skills. But in case of Urdu medium students parents are not serious for providing these things to their children. This affects on Urdu medium students both internally and physically. As compared to Urdu medium students English medium students have all these aspects. Due to these facilities English medium students are fully satisfied.

The mean scores of family climate of secondary girls are higher than the boys. This could be due to the fact that now a day's girls and boys get equal support from their parents but girls take benefit from these supports because they are very close to their family and share their joys, sadness, thoughts etc freely. Instead boys like to share their problems, thoughts, joys with their friends. This could be the reason for low mean score of boys.

The mean scores of peer group participation of English medium students is higher than the Urdu medium students. This could be due to the fact that peers are responsible for developing one's behavior, peers provide good knowledge of things in a better way. One can understand wrong and right good and bad thing easily, through peers. Due to lack of peer's participation Urdu medium students are unable to share their views and ideas to other people. They always search for students to share it. But English medium students create good and effective peers for discussing their difficulties and they get various good views on a certain topics.

The mean scores of peer group participation for secondary girls are higher than the boys. This could be due to the fact that in ancient time parents did not allowed girls to make their friends by choice. Due to the advancement of education parents allow their girls to make friends by their choice. This could be the reason of high mean score of girls.

The mean score of extra-curricular activities for English medium students is higher than the Urdu medium students. This could be due to the fact that English medium students parents allow their children to participate in any programmes such as essay competitions, oratorical contents and musical competitions, active interest in sports and games, involvement in group work such as taking part in dramas, ability in histrionic talents and the liking for excursion etc. But rarely parents of Urdu medium students give freedom to their children to participate in such types of activity. Extra curricular activities provide confidence to students. It is a one kind of school for students, it teaches leadership quality, brotherhood, national integration etc.

The mean scores of extra curricular activities for secondary girls is higher than the boys. This could be due to the reason that girls are very interested to get knowledge from educational

places and they insist their parents for visit it. They explain the importance and need of recreational places to their parents. But boys are not very much interested to visit such kind of places. So this could be the reason for low mean score of boys.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

Home life experience in terms of educational encouragement, family climate is very important part in a childhood state. It helps us in improving child's personality. Family climate provides the value of love, affection, care, truthfulness and self-confidence while extracurricular activities and peer group participation give boost which required achieving success in life. From the study it is found that English medium students get better home life experience than Urdu medium students. Similarly, English medium girls get better home life experience than English medium boys, Urdu medium girls and Urdu medium boys.

Acknowledgements: The researcher wishes to express her deepest and most sincere gratitude to her M.Ed. student Ms. Rukhsana Bi Mohd Kamil for translating the tool in Urdu.

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